

Comparison of insecticide reaction of greenhouse and F₂ populations of field-collected GLH, IRRI, Feb 1984.

Insecticide	LD ₅₀ ^a (μg/g 24 h)		Difference (F-GH)	ERR ^c
	Field-collected population (F)	Greenhouse population (GH)		
BPMC	5.11	2.86	2.25 ns	1.79
Carbaryl	7.01	4.40	2.61 ns	1.59
Carbofuran	2.40	0.99	1.41 ns	2.42
Diazinon	26.41	8.23	18.24*	3.22
Monocrotophos	9.16	6.25	2.91 ns	1.47

^a Av of 3 replications (20 adult females/replication). ^b* = significant at 5%, ns = not significant.

^c Estimated resistance ratio = $\frac{LD_{50} \text{ value for F}}{LD_{50} \text{ value for GH}}$.

was from 1.47 to 3.22. This indicates that the field-collected GLH may be developing resistance to the tested insecticides. Only the diazinon-treated field-collected population was significantly more resistant than the greenhouse culture (see table). □

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Pest Control and Management

OTHER PESTS

Alternate foods of bandicoot rats in deep water rice areas of Bangladesh

Md. Sayed Ahmed, Entomology Division, Bangladesh Rice Research Institute, and E. Haque and J. E. Brooks, Bangladesh Agricultural Research Institute, Joydebpur, Dhaka, Bangladesh

While conducting rodent control experiments in deep water rice areas of Tangail district in 1983, we found that rats ate snails, water lily fruit, and water hyacinth stems. In early 1984, we visited the same area to record rodent damage to boro rice. There were many bandicoot rat burrows near the dike of the boro rice field, but there was little rodent damage. To determine what the rats were eating, we excavated a burrow system (see figure) and found 68 modified stems of *Nymphaea lotus* (715 g) and 32 snail shells (*Pila globosa* and *Viviparus bengalensis*) in the food chamber. In laboratory tests we found that bandicoot rats can easily live on *P. globosa* and tubers of *N. lotus* (see table). Farmers often use the tubers of *N. lotus* as food during crisis, and 1 kg costs about \$0.25 during the season. Snails are fed to ducks. We also found eight rat litters in the same burrow system. □

Bandicoot rat burrow system in a dike during boro season in a deep water rice are in Bangladesh.

Body weight increase of *Bandicota indica* after 5 d feeding on snails and tubers. Bangladesh Agricultural Research Institute, 1984.

Food ^a	Amount consumed (g/d)			Body weight (g)		Increase (%)
	Min	Max	Mean	Prefeeding	Postfeeding	
Snail	28.0	96.0	61.8	442.0	451.0	2
Tuber	37.0	49.0	42.2			
Snail	0.0	80.0	34.6	287.0	287.0	0
Tuber	5.0	37.0	26.2			
Snail	31.0	90.0	64.0	242.0	277.0	14
Tuber	45.0	69.0	56.8			

^a Snail = *Pila globosa*, tuber = modified stems of *Nymphaea lotus*.

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